

The Dark Sides of Modern Science: Publishing and Dissemination (Part I)

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Abstract: This is the second article in our series “The Dark Sides of Modern Science” and is about publishing and dissemination of science (and knowledge in general). As the subject of “publishing and dissemination of science” is too big, we decided to divide it in more than one part. The remarks that we stated in the Introduction of the first article of this series (i.e. “Knowledge Production and Authoring”) generally apply to this article and hence we do not need to repeat.

Keywords: Academic publishing, dissemination of knowledge, ethics of science, ethics of publishing, ethics of knowledge dissemination, morality in science, academic misconduct, corruption in science, corruption related to science.

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1 Simultaneous, Duplicate and Multiple Submissions

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 32. The dawn of the age of duplicate peer review.
 33. Introduction to Guidelines on Multiple Submission and Prior Publication.
 34. Is it time to rewrite the rules on duplicate submission in the age of preprints?.
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 36. Taylor & Francis Pilots Duplicate Submission Detection Tool.
 37. Reevaluating the Single Submission Rule in Scholarly Publishing.
 38. Simultaneous & Duplicate Submissions, Interesting Cases.
 39. Duplicate publications and simultaneous submissions.
 40. The Impact of Duplicate Submission: Protecting Your Academic and Professional Rep-

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42. [Simultaneous & Duplicate Submissions, Ethics.](#)
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82. Multiple, duplicate, concurrent publication/simultaneous submission.
83. Duplicate publications and simultaneous submissions.
84. Repetitive duplicate submission to multiple journals and redundant publication.
85. Understanding Redundant Publication and Salami Slicing in Research.
86. Overlapping Publications.
87. Simultaneous Submission.
88. Acceptable Secondary Publication: Publishing the same research in Multiple Languages.
89. Overlapping Publication.
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91. Overlapping Publications.
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93. Inadvertent duplicate publication of the same article a month apart in the same journal.
94. Originality and duplication in scientific publications.
95. Image duplication in scientific papers: how AI outperforms humans at detecting research misconduct.
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97. Journals are failing to address duplication in the literature, says a new study.
98. Addressing duplicate submission in academic publishing: Who bears responsibility?.
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15 Censorship

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